

ABSTRACT

Educational tours are extracurricular activities that allow students to explore possibilities other than classroom instruction. It supplements the learning of students since educators believe that learning does not only occur within the four walls of the classroom. This descriptive-comparative determines the influencing factors that affect the participation of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration students in educational tours implemented by a tertiary educational institution in Quezon City. A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized among the 490 students. The findings indicate that socialization and encouragement to others are considered highly influential factors in students' participation in educational tours. Moreover, personal gain, fun, and travel are highly influential among students regardless of their demographics. Finally, encouragement to others is the only influential factor with significant differences among students when grouped according to their year level.

Keywords: *Influencing Factors, BSBA, Educational Tour, Tertiary Educational Institution, Quezon City*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most memorable moments of being a student is the activities, especially those conducted outside the campus or the so-called educational tours activities. In selected educational institutions in Quezon City, each department participates in tours guided by the provision of school guidelines, and a third-party company is assigned to monitor the activity flow of the program. Educational tour activities are the co-curricular activities of every Higher Education Institution which are not part of the school's curriculum (Jackson & Rowe, 2023). All co-curricular pursuits enhance a formal education. Although some of these activities, like high school programs, can be organized by age group, that is only sometimes the case. Some could work part-time or volunteer with a nearby nonprofit, for instance. As cited by Bauman and Lucy (2021), all employers are searching for college students and recent graduates with various talents, character traits, and professional experience that will enable them to succeed in the workplace. Participating in things we enjoy, educational tours, and co-curricular activities allow us the chance to improve these skills. During the pandemic period, the cultural, educational tour, and co-curricular activities of the selected educational institution were postponed due to the policies and guidelines of the local and national governments.

Learning within classrooms and learning by Experience may differ for every individual; some things are not taught inside the classroom. Thus, applying the principles and theories explained by the professors can only be experienced in the field of operation (Bada & Olusegun, 2015). As mentioned in the study of Uy et al. (2021), they thought their lessons were aided by the abilities they saw in the individuals and tourism professionals they met on these visits. These excursions were designed to extend the knowledge and expertise of tourism students in preparation for their future employment in the sector. Also, students could learn at their own pace while on an educational tour; instead of using text or abstract presentations, this learning tool stimulated the mind and the pupils' interest (Martinez Casanovas et al., 2022). Furthermore, Bell et al. (2016) highlighted the benefits of having an educational excursion where students might learn about the culture by corresponding with locals and chatting with people, and learning about the locations from the residents' perspectives would help the learner become more understanding of regional traditions, values, and beliefs. Students may need help understanding concepts that apply to them; with experiential learning, students can apply information and thoughts in a context where they also actively participate in the real world. As the student converses with the teacher, information takes on a life of its own (Uy, 2018)

At present, since the new normal has lessened its intensity in terms of restrictions, the sensitivity has been declining too, to the extent that outside and gathering activities are somewhat allowed to be conducted; for this reason, such as face-to-face classes, religious meetings, and even parties and celebrations. The selected educational institution in Quezon City is now back on providing educational tour activities or off-campus activities; based on the Inquirer (2022), Senator Cayetano, who is the sponsor of the Dep-Ed budget, stated that "*Provision No. 6 under Department Order No. 34 series of 2022 states co-curricular and educational tour programs may be conducted throughout the school year*" who also clarified that there is no ban in educational tour activities or off-campus activities (Fernandez, 2022).

According to CHED Memorandum Order No. 63 Series of 2017, Through the execution of off-campus activities, higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines maintain a sustainable

teaching and learning delivery process. These are activities carried out by HEIs in addition to the typical classroom instruction to support and encourage a more fulfilling learning experience for students. Programs that meet the requirements of a particular degree program. These also consist of educational tour pursuits. They are a solid motivator to develop the connection between academia and industry because they are designed to increase students' learning chances and give them a taste of the real world. These educational opportunities include internships, excursions, field studies, educational connections, student development activities, educational tour pursuits like volunteer work, inter-school contests, immersion/reach-out programs, conventions, conferences, training sessions, cultural performances, and team-building exercises. All HEIs are given the authority to conduct off-campus activities in selected educational institutions in Quezon City; most off-campus activities are conducted per year level. Specifically in the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration and Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship programs, educational tour activities include National Service Training Program camping for First-year level and Business Tours and Seminars for Second-year, Third-year, and Fourth-year level.

The educational tour activities of the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration are being promoted and marketed by the faculty members to encourage students to participate in the provided seminars and tours by the school administration. The Bachelor of Science in Business Administration is one of the programs with many populations. Based on the department's official record, there are currently 3,203 students for the academic year 2022-2023 1st semester. Noticeably, despite the incentives, promotion, and encouragement on how enjoyable the activity would be, students, for some reason, have not been able to participate or decided not to participate in educational tour activities.

The tallied and official record from the department and Management Information System of the selected tertiary educational institution, students from the First-year level, which consists of 1147 students, 64% percent or 730 students have participated in off-campus activities while 408 students have not. From Second-year and Third-year students, there are 1171 participants (or 86%) of the educational tour, while 198 students contribute 14% of non-participants. Furthermore, at the Fourth-year level, there are 610 students (or 89 %) who participated in the educational tour' while 77 students contributed to 11 percent of students who have not participated.

The data mentioned and presented above led the researcher to examine the factors influencing the students to participate in educational tours and how influential those factors are. For these reasons, the researchers explored the factors that influence students' participation in the off-campus activities of selected tertiary educational institutions in Quezon City.

Previous studies have identified the factors that influence students' participation in particular activities through thematic analysis and coding. The study by Phelps (2017) identified the reasons for students' participation in activities: encouragement from others, personal gain, social component, and fun and travel. These factors emerged upon careful coding and analysis through a thematic analysis based on the participants' answers in the previous study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This research utilized the quantitative-descriptive research design. The quantitative research method refers to collecting and analyzing numerical data. The Quantitative-descriptive research design is used to assess the level of influence of the factors on students' participation, such as socialization & encouragement from others, financial capability, personal gain, and fun & travel. In addition, the evaluation of the levels of the variables' influence is compared in accordance with the student's year level.

Respondents. The study's respondents have enrolled students from the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program who have joined the previous educational tour activities within the academic year 2022-2023. There are 2,511 total students enrolled from the First-year level to the Fourth-year level based on the official record from the Bachelor of Science in Business Administration program; the researcher utilized Slovin's calculation to determine the exact number of sample size in which the data gathering is administered, which generated a total of 334 sample size. The sample size required for a specific population is determined using G-Power Sample Size Calculator. The G-Power Sample Size Calculator is applied when the population is significant and homogeneous. The researchers have utilized the G-Power Sample Size Calculator, which is a method used in statistical analysis to establish the required population sample size for a particular study. Only when the sample size is uncertain is this formula employed; therefore, it is logical for this study to use this calculation method to identify the specific sample size needed. However, the researchers reached beyond the

expected total sample population. The researchers administered the survey questionnaires to a total of 490 students.

Data Collection Procedure. The survey questionnaire is administered to the respondents by disseminating Google forms to social media platforms, particularly Facebook and Messenger. Informed consent is also presented to emphasize the rights of the respondents to decide whether they will participate or not in the study. In addition, the assurance of the right to privacy and confidentiality is observed. The respondents' answers were automatically saved on the Google form and extracted as an Excel file. The data in the Excel file is processed using statistical software that is used to analyze and interpret data.

Data Analysis Procedure. The researchers used *to mean* to serve as a standard for all observations by serving to reflect the average value and encapsulate a whole data set into a single integer that represents the midpoint or typical value of the data. To determine the right statistical treatment of data, the researchers utilized the Shapiro-Wilk to determine the normality of the gathered data. Since the data is considered abnormal in distribution, the researchers utilized nonparametric data. The assumptions for using Kruskal-Wallis Test are associated with the collected data to conclude if the respective tool is reliable and valid to carefully analyze the data and answer the research queries presented in the study. The completed surveys are examined using the Kruskal-Wallis Test to determine the difference between and among the variables. The Kruskal-Wallis Test is executed through statistical software for the treatment of data. Kruskal-Wallis Test is a rank-based nonparametric test that can be used to determine if there are statistically significant differences between two or more groups of an independent variable on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable. Therefore, it is the most appropriate tool for the study since the researcher determines the difference in the level of influence each year based on the cited influencing factors. The researcher also used the arithmetic mean to determine the mean of the given variables, such as Socialization, Encouragement from others, Financial Capability, Personal Gain, and Fun and Travel. The researcher used the Likert Scale to evaluate the total mean of the gathered data of students' participation and the level of influence in each year level. The highest evaluation is five as Very Highly Influential, four as Highly Influential, three as Influential, two as Moderately Influential, and one as Least Influential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents as to Age

Table 3.1 above shows the profile of the respondents according to age. The results show that the majority of the respondents were 21 to 25 years, contributing 52% percent of the population and had the highest ranking; also, 44% percent of the population, or 217 respondents, were 16 to 20 years old, ranked second highest. Furthermore, 3% of the respondents, or 16 people, were 26 years old to 30 years old, which got the third rank. Moreover, 31 above contributed the lowest with a percentage of 1% or four people in frequency. According to Know the Questions (2017), age, talents, and the number of students are always considered while planning educational tours, mainly since those elements are the main reasons the school is holding the activity in the first place. Additionally, those planning the trips ensure the programs are age-appropriate ("Know the Questions, "2017).

Table 3.1

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
16-20	217	44%	2
21-25	253	52%	1
26-30	16	3%	3
31 Above	4	1%	4
Total	490	100%	

Profile of the Respondents as to Gender

Table 3.2 represents the distribution of the profile of the respondents as to gender. Results show that most respondents were female, contributing to 75% percent of the population or 368 respondents, and is the highest ranking. Also, male respondents had a frequency of 118, or 24% percent of the population. Moreover, another gender, such as bisexual, gay, and transgender, got the lowest ranking with a percentage of 1% or four respondents in frequency. This result is congruent with the study of Leraas et al. (2018), which claimed that females participated more compared to males. However, Leeras et al. (2018) argued that students' participation might be impacted by aspects such as sex, psychological gender, and personality. Much research has been done on the relationship between

student engagement and the sex of the lecturer and students. However, according to a study by Aguillon (2020), male students participate less than male students.

Table 3.2

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	118	24%	2
Female	368	75%	1
Other	4	1%	3
Total	490	100%	

Profile of the Respondents as to Year Level

Table 3.3 presents the distribution of the respondents according to year level. Second-year students got the highest percentage, with 51% contributing to 249 respondents. Students in the Third-year level ranked 2 with a percentage of 21% or 105 respondents. Furthermore, First-year students got 18% percent with a frequency of 87 respondents. Lastly, students in a Fourth-year level got the lowest percentage with 10% or 49 respondents.

Table 3.3

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
First-year	87	18%	4
Second-year	249	51%	3
Third-year	105	21%	1
Fourth-year	49	10%	2
Total	490	100%	

Level of Influence as to Socialization of Fourth-year BSBA Students

Table 3.4 presents the level of influence of socialization on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. Indicators were answered by the respondents with the use of an influential 5-point scale. The indicator [*the thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.*] got the highest rank with a mean of 3.48, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential, while the [*The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.69, verbally interpreted as Highly influential.

Furthermore, indicators [The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.] and [Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.] got the third rank with a mean of 3.63. Moreover, [The idea of acquiring new friends] ranked second lowest with a mean of 3.57, in which all were verbally interpreted as Highly influential. The results supported by the study of Engberg et al. (2018) found that off-campus activities contribute to the career development of the students, as they feel fulfilled and find purpose in their lives, which urges them to feel the excitement of anticipating socialization with their fellow students and push them to engage with off-campus activities.

Table 3.4

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.]	3.69	Highly Influential	2
[Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.]	3.63	Highly Influential	3
[The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.]	3.63	Highly Influential	3
[The idea of acquiring new friends]	3.57	Highly Influential	4
[The thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.]	3.96	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to encouragement from others of Fourth-year BSBA students

Table 3.5 presents the level of influence of encouragement from others on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicators [*Encouragement from my teachers*] and [*Encouragement from my friends and fellow students*] got the highest rank with a mean of 3.65, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential, while the [*The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.51, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator [*Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.*] got the third rank with a mean of 3.35. Moreover, [*Feedback I hear from previous joiners*] placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.24, in which all were verbally interpreted as Highly influential. The study by Engelberg (2018) stressed that students who witnessed their "senior" students who participated in off-campus activities, especially those who gave positive feedback about their experiences, are more likely to be encouraged to join in off-campus activities, which leads to more excitement and anticipation of the sense of enjoyment.

Table 3.5

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]	3.65	Highly Influential	1
[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]	3.24	Influential	4
[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]	3.35	Influential	3
[Encouragement from my teachers]	3.65	Highly Influential	1
[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]	3.51	Highly Influential	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Financial Capability of Fourth-year BSBA Students

Table 3.6 presents the level of influence of financial capability on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicator [*Cost of the off-campus activities*] got the highest rank with a mean of 2.90, which is verbally interpreted as Influential, while the indicator [*Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 2.80, verbally interpreted as influential. Furthermore, indicator [*Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-*

Campus activity.] got the third rank with a mean of 2.76 which was verbally interpreted as Influential. Also, *[Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.]* placed as the second lowest ranking with a mean of 2.69 with a verbal interpretation as Influential. Lastly, *[Having a financially stable family.]* got the lowest with a verbal interpretation Influential with a mean of 2.53. The study results by Suarez et al. (2017) highlight that most students who are about to join educational tours and trips consider their financial capability. Students consider that educational tours are costly.

Table 3.6

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.	2.76	Influential	3
Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.	2.84	Influential	2
Cost of the off-campus activities.	2.90	Influential	1
Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.	2.69	Influential	4
Having a financially stable family.	2.53	Influential	5
Overall Weighted Mean	2.74	Influential	

Level of Influence as to Personal Gain of Fourth-year BSBA Students

Table 3.7 presents the level of influence of Personal Gain on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicator *[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]* got the highest rank with a mean of 3.94, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Seeing different perspectives of learning]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.86, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Able to share my experiences with others]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.84, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Also, *[Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]* ranked second lowest with a mean of 3.82 and a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]* got the lowest ranking with a verbal interpretation of Highly Influential and a mean of 2.53. Hans et al. (2017) found that academic incentives can increase participation; this suggests that promoting educational tours with incentives is related to the student's willingness to participate in out-of-the-school activities. Kennedy (2014) contends that one of the critical elements of an educational tour is gaining something meaningful, achieving the sense of enrichment of their purpose, and the students have fun while still learning something new.

Table 3.7

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]	3.76	Highly Influential	5
[Seeing different perspectives of learning]	3.86	Highly Influential	2
[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]	3.94	Highly Influential	1
Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]	3.82	Highly Influential	4
[Able to share my experiences with other people]	3.84	Highly Influential	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.84	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to the Fun and Travel of Fourth-year BSBA Students

Table 3.7 presents the level of influence of Fun and Travel on Fourth-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicator *[Goal to have beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.06, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]* and *[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.02, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.86, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]* placed as the lowest ranking with a mean of 3.82 with a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. As cited in the study by Roberson (2018), in general, travel for both leisure and education has increased over the world, especially in locations that are seen as safe (Stone & Petrick, 2013), both Independent and inexpensive travel (O'Reilly, 2006). The study also claimed that travel can promote learning about oneself, the world, trust, and home. This explains why having fun and traveling contributes to the student's participation in educational tours.

Table 3.8

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Goal to have a beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]	4.06	Highly Influential	1
[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]	4.02	Highly Influential	2
[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]	4.02	Highly Influential	2
[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]	3.86	Highly Influential	3
[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]	3.82	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.96	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Socialization of Third-year BSBA Students

Table 3.9 presents the level of influence of socialization to Third-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicator *[The thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.11, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. At the same time, the *[Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.03, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.]* and got the third rank with a mean of 3.99.

Moreover, *[The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.]* placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.57, in which all were verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Lastly, indicator *[The idea of acquiring new friends]* got the lowest ranking with a mean of 3.76 with the verbal interpretation of Highly influential. According to research by Engberg et al. (2018), off-campus activities help students develop their careers because they feel fulfilled and have a purpose in life, which motivates them to participate in off-campus activities because they anticipate socializing with other students.

Table 3.9

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>[The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.]</i>	3.99	Highly Influential	3
<i>[Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.]</i>	4.03	Highly Influential	2
<i>[The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.]</i>	3.93	Highly Influential	4
<i>[The idea of acquiring new friends]</i>	3.76	Highly Influential	5
<i>[The thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.]</i>	4.11	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.97	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to encouragement from others of Third-year BSBA students

Table 3.10 presents the level of influence of encouragement from others on Third-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of a selected educational institution in Quezon City. The indicators *[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.0, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the *[Encouragement from my teachers]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.96, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, the indicator *[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.90.

Moreover, *[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]* placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.88, in which all were verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Lastly, *[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]* got the lowest ranking with a mean of 3.63 with a verbal interpretation of Highly Influential. The study by Engelberg (2018) stressed that students who witnessed their "senior" students who participated in off-campus activities, especially those who gave positive feedback about their experiences, are more likely to be encouraged to join in off-campus activities, which leads to more excitement and anticipation of the sense of enjoyment.

Table 3.10

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]	3.90	Highly Influential	3
[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]	3.63	Highly Influential	5
[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]	3.88	Highly Influential	4
[Encouragement from my teachers]	3.96	Highly Influential	2
[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]	4.00	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence Financial Capability to Third-year BSBA Students.

Table 3.11 presents the level of influence of financial capability on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.* got the highest rank with a mean of 3.02, which is verbally interpreted as Influential. In contrast, the indicator *Cost of the off-campus activities.* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.00, verbally interpreted as influential. Furthermore, indicator *Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.* got the third rank with a mean of 2.99, verbally interpreted as Influential. Also, *Having a financially stable family.* and *Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.* placed as the lowest ranking with a mean of 2.90 with a verbal interpretation as Influential. The study results by Suarez et al. (2017) highlight that most students who are about to join educational tours and trips consider their financial capability. Students consider that educational tours are very expensive.

Table 3.11

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.	2.90	Influential	4
Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.	3.02	Influential	1
Cost of the off-campus activities.	3.00	Influential	2
Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.	2.99	Influential	3
Having a financially stable family.	2.90	Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	2.96	Influential	

Level of Influence as to Personal Gain of Third-year BSBA Students

Table 3.12 presents the level of influence of Personal Gain on 3rd BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.16, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.07, verbally interpreted as Highly

influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Able to share my experiences with other people]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.84, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Also, *[Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]]* ranked second lowest with a mean of 3.82 and a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]* got the lowest ranking with a verbal interpretation of Highly Influential and a mean of 2.53. Hans et al. (2017) found that academic incentives can increase participation; this suggests that promoting educational tours with the inclusion of incentives is related to the student's willingness to participate in out-of-the-school activities. Kennedy (2014) contends that one of the critical elements of an educational tour is gaining something meaningful that is achieving the sense of enrichment of their purpose, that the students are having fun while still learning something new.

Table 3.12

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]	4.16	Highly Influential	1
[Seeing different perspectives of learning]	4.05	Highly Influential	3
[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]	4.07	Highly Influential	2
Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]	3.98	Highly Influential	5
[Able to share my experiences with other people]	4.04	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	4.06	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to the Fun and Travel of Third-year BSBA Students

Table 3.13 presents the level of influence of fun and travel on BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Goal to have beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.06, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]* and *[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.02, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.86, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]* placed as the lowest ranking with a mean of 3.82 with a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. As cited in the study by Roberson (2018), in general, travel for both leisure and education has increased over the world, especially in locations that are seen as safe (Stone & Petrick, 2013), both Independent and inexpensive travel (O'Reilly, 2006). The study also claimed that travel can promote learning about oneself, the world, trust, and home. This explains why having fun and traveling contributes to the student's participation in educational tours.

Table 3.13

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Goal to have a beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]	4.25	Highly Influential	1
[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]	4.21	Highly Influential	2
[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]	4.19	Highly Influential	3
[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]	3.99	Highly Influential	5
[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]	4.08	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	4.14	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Socialization of Second-year BSBA Students

Table 3.14 presents the level of influence of socialization on Second-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator [*the thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.*] got the highest rank with a mean of 4.01, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential, while the [*Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.92, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicators [*The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.*] got the third rank with a mean of 3.80.

Moreover, [*The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.*] placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.75, with a verbal interpretation of Highly Influential. Lastly, [*The idea of acquiring new friends*] got the lowest rank with a mean of 3.74, interpreted as Highly Influential. Based on the findings of the Engberg et al. (2018) study, students who participate in off-campus activities find fulfillment and a sense of purpose in their lives, which motivates them to get involved in off-campus activities because they anticipate interacting with other students.

Table 3.14

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.]	3.80	Highly Influential	3
[Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.]	3.92	Highly Influential	2
[The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.]	3.75	Highly Influential	4
[The idea of acquiring new friends]	3.74	Highly Influential	5
[The thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.]	4.01	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.84	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to encouragement from others of Second-year BSBA students

Table 3.15 presents the level of influence of encouragement from others on Second-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City.

The indicators [*The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.*] got the highest rank with a mean of 3.79, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential, while the [*Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.*] and [*Encouragement from my teachers*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.71 verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Moreover, [*Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.*] placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.88, interpreted as Highly influential. Lastly, [*Feedback I heard from previous joiners*] got the lowest ranking of 3.63, which was interpreted as Highly Influential. The study by Engelberg (2018) stressed that students who witnessed their "senior" students who participated in off-campus activities, especially those who gave positive feedback about their experiences, are more likely to be encouraged to join in off-campus activities, which leads to more excitement and anticipation of the sense of enjoyment.

Table 3.15

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]	3.67	Highly Influential	3
[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]	3.47	Highly Influential	4
[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]	3.71	Highly Influential	2
[Encouragement from my teachers]	3.71	Highly Influential	2
[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]	3.79	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Financial Capability of Second-year BSBA Students

Table 3.16 presents the level of influence of financial capability on Second-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator [*Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.*] got the highest rank with a mean of 3.02, which is verbally interpreted as Influential, while the indicator [*Cost of the off-campus activities.*] got the second highest in ranking with a mean of 3.00, verbally interpreted as influential. Furthermore, the indicator [*Is capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.*] got the third rank with a mean of 2.99 which was verbally interpreted as Influential. Also, [*Having a financially stable family.*] and [*Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.*] placed as the lowest ranking with a mean of 2.90 with a verbal interpretation as Influential. The study results by Suarez et al. (2017) highlight that most students who are about to join educational tours and trips consider their financial capability. Students consider that educational tours are costly.

Table 3.16

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.	2.74	Influential	4
Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.	2.85	Influential	1
Cost of the off-campus activities.	2.96	Influential	2
Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.	2.84	Influential	3
Having a financially stable family.	2.75	Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	2.83	Influential	

Level of Influence as to Personal Gain of Second-year BSBA Students

Table 3.17 presents the level of influence of Personal Gain on Second-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.16, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.07, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Seeing different perspectives of learning]* got the third rank with a mean of 4.05, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Also, *[Able to share my experiences with other people]* ranked second lowest with a mean of 4.04 and a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]* got the lowest ranking with a verbal interpretation Highly Influential and a mean of 3.98. Hans et al. (2017) found that academic incentives can increase participation; this suggests that promoting educational tours with incentives is related to the student's willingness to participate in out-of-the-school activities. Kennedy (2014) contends that one of the critical elements of an educational tour is gaining something meaningful that is achieving the sense of enrichment of their purpose, that the students are having fun while still learning something new.

Table 3.17

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]	4.16	Highly Influential	1
[Seeing different perspectives of learning]	4.05	Highly Influential	3
[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]	4.07	Highly Influential	2
Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]	3.98	Highly Influential	5
[Able to share my experiences with other people]	4.04	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	4.06	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to the Fun and Travel of Second-year BSBA Students

Table 3.18 presents the level of influence of fun and travel on Second-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Goal to have beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.22, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]* and *[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.21, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]* got the third rank with a mean of 4.19, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]* placed as the second lowest ranking with a mean of 4.08 with a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]* got the lowest ranking with a verbal interpretation of Highly influential and a mean of 3.99. As cited in the study by Roberson (2018), in general, travel for both leisure and education has increased over the world, especially in locations that are seen as safe (Stone & Petrick, 2013), both Independent and inexpensive travel (O'Reilly, 2006). The study also claimed that travel can promote learning about oneself, the world, trust, and home. This explains why having fun and traveling contributes to the student's participation in educational tours.

Table 3.18

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Goal to have a beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]	4.22	Highly Influential	1
[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]	4.21	Highly Influential	2
[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]	4.19	Highly Influential	3
[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]	3.99	Highly Influential	5
[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]	4.08	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	4.14	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Socialization of First-year BSBA Students

Table 3.19 presents the level of influence of socialization on First-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator [*the thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.*] got the highest rank with a mean of 3.85, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the [*The idea of acquiring new friends*] got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.68, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicators [*Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.*] got the third rank with a mean of 3.63.

Moreover, [*The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.*] placed as the second lowest with a mean of 3.53, with a verbal interpretation of Highly Influential. Lastly, [*The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.*] got the lowest rank, which was 3.52, which was interpreted as Highly Influential. The findings of Engberg et al. (2018) in his study emphasized that students who participate in off-campus activities find fulfillment and a sense of purpose in their lives, which motivates them to get involved in off-campus activities because they anticipate interacting with other students.

Table 3.19

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[The idea of nurturing relationships with my fellow students on educational trips.]	3.52	Highly Influential	5
[Excitement arises whenever we have educational trips with my friends and classmates.]	3.63	Highly Influential	3
[The thought of my friends and classmates joining too.]	3.53	Highly Influential	4
[The idea of acquiring new friends]	3.68	Highly Influential	2
[The thought of exploring new things with my friends and classmates in educational tours.]	3.85	Highly Influential	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.64	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to encouragement from others of First-year BSBA students

Table 3.20 presents the level of influence of encouragement from others on First-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicators [*Encouragement from my friends and fellow students*] got the highest rank with a mean of

3.68, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential, while the *[Encouragement from my teachers]* and *[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.49, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, the indicator *[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]* ranked third with a mean of 3.90. Moreover, *[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]* ranked second lowest with a mean of 3.45, interpreted as Highly influential. Lastly, *[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]* got the lowest ranking with a mean of 3.39, interpreted as Highly Influential. The study by Engelberg (2018) stressed that students who witnessed their "senior" students who participated in off-campus activities, especially those who gave positive feedback about their experiences, are more likely to be encouraged to join in off-campus activities, which leads to more excitement and anticipation of the sense of enjoyment.

Table 3.20

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>[Encouragement from my friends and fellow students]</i>	3.68	Highly Influential	1
<i>[Feedback I hear from previous joiners]</i>	3.45	Influential	3
<i>[Promotion of teachers about the activities of the educational tours.]</i>	3.39	Influential	4
<i>[Encouragement from my teachers]</i>	3.49	Influential	2
<i>[The thought that I can hang out with my friends on educational tours.]</i>	3.49	Influential	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to Financial Capability of First-year BSBA Students

Table 3.21 presents the level of influence of financial capability on First-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Cost of the off-campus activities.]* got the highest rank with a mean of 2.93, which is verbally interpreted as Influential, while the indicator *[Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.]* got the second highest in ranking with a mean of 2.72, verbally interpreted as influential. Furthermore, indicators *[Having a financially stable family.]* got the third rank with a mean of 2.62, verbally interpreted as Influential. Also, *[Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity]* placed as the second lowest ranking with a mean of 2.61 with a verbal interpretation as Influential. Lastly, *[Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.]* got the lowest rank with a mean of 2.57. The study results by Suarez et al. (2017) highlight that most students who are about to join educational tours and trips consider their financial capability. Students consider that educational tours are costly.

Table 3.21

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Having enough financial resources for the expenses of the Off-Campus activity.	2.61	Influential	4
Being capable of allocating fees for the additional payments related to school.	2.72	Influential	2
Cost of the off-campus activities.	2.93	Influential	1
Being capable of saving allowance given by parents for the expense of off-campus activities.	2.57	Influential	5
Having a financially stable family.	2.62	Influential	3
Overall Weighted Mean	2.71	Influential	

Level of Influence as to Personal Gain of First-year BSBA Students

Table 3.22 presents the level of influence of Personal Gain on First-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]* got the highest rank with a mean of 3.83, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the Personal indicator *Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]* and *[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 3.80, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Seeing different perspectives of learning]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.74, verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. Also, *[Able to share my experiences with other people]* ranked at the lowest with a mean of 3.70 and a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Hans et al. (2017) found that academic incentives can increase participation; this suggests that promoting educational tours with incentives is related to the student's willingness to participate in out-of-the-school activities. Kennedy (2014) contends that one of the critical elements of an educational tour is gaining something meaningful that is achieving the sense of enrichment of their purpose, that the students are having fun while still learning something new.

Table 3.22

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Obtaining academic incentives such as additional points for grades and examination exemptions]	3.80	Highly Influential	2
[Seeing different perspectives of learning]	3.74	Highly Influential	3
[Earning more experiences and other information that is not being studied inside of a classroom]	3.83	Highly Influential	1
Personal Gain [Discovering my career path and purpose in life]	3.80	Highly Influential	2
[Able to share my experiences with other people]	3.70	Highly Influential	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.77	Highly Influential	

Level of Influence as to the Fun and Travel of First-year BSBA Students

Table 3.23 presents the level of influence of fun and travel on First-year BSBA students' participation in educational tours of selected educational institutions in Quezon City. The indicator *[Goal to have beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]* got the highest rank with a mean of 4.01, which is verbally interpreted as Highly Influential. In contrast, the indicator *[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]* got the second highest ranking with a mean of 4.00, verbally interpreted as Highly influential. Furthermore, indicator *[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]* got the third rank with a mean of 3.98, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Influential.

Moreover, *[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]* ranked second lowest with a mean of 3.94 with a verbal interpretation as Highly Influential. Lastly, *[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]* got the lowest ranking with a verbal interpretation of Highly influential and a mean of 3.59. As cited in the study by Roberson (2018), in general, travel for both leisure and education has increased over the world, especially in locations that are seen as safe (Stone & Petrick, 2013), both Independent and inexpensive travel (O'Reilly, 2006). The study also claimed that travel can promote learning about oneself, the world, trust, and home. This explains why having fun and traveling contributes to the student's participation in educational tours.

Table 3.23

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
[Goal to have a beautiful memories with my fellow students to recall later in life]	4.01	Highly Influential	1
[Adventure to places to explore and have fun]	3.94	Highly Influential	4
[Experience of traveling and unwinding once in a while]	4.00	Highly Influential	2
[Transportation and accommodation arrangement]	3.59	Highly Influential	5
[Fun activities and learning on educational trips.]	3.98	Highly Influential	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.90	Highly Influential	

Significant Difference in the Influencing Factors

Based on the significance levels, it is indicated in Table 3.24 that there is a significant difference between the level of influence of encouragement to others to students' participation when grouped according to year level (significance level of 0.015). In terms of encouragement to others, the Third-year (mean rank of 278.42) is the most influenced by the stated factor in order to participate in students' educational tour, followed by the Second-year (mean rank of 245.92), First-year (mean rank of 221.83), and Fourth-year (214.83). Following the study of Suarez (2017), most individuals in the Third-year are the most to participate in educational tours due to the motivational encouragement of their seniors (Fourth-year) towards them. In addition, first-year undergraduate college students are more likely to participate in educational trips and tours as they seem to be very active in socialization and bloom curiosity because first-year students are "new" and "first-timer" in encountering different activities (Egerberg et al., 2018). On the other hand, there is no significant difference between the level of influence of socialization (significance level of 0.061), financial capability (significance level of 0.241), personal gain (significance level of .181), and fun and travel (significance level of .385) to student's participation on educational tours when grouped according to year level. The role of socialization, financial capability, personal gain, and fun and travel have the same level of influence regardless of the student's year level towards participation in educational tours (Harazneh et al., 2020).

Table 3.24

	Socialization	Encouragement	Financial Capability	Personal Gain	Fun and Travel
Chi-Square	7.355	10.480	4.195	4.878	3.046
df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.61	.015	.241	.181	.385

CONCLUSION

The researchers conclude that the majority of the students who decide to participate in educational tours are female. Also, the researchers conclude that female students are more likely to participate in educational tours than male students. Moreover, most respondents are presently enrolled as Second-year students, followed by Third-year students, Fourth-year students, and First-year students.

Socialization is a highly influential factor among Third-year, Second-year, Fourth-year, and First-year students. In terms of encouragement to others, it has the greatest influence on Third-year students, followed by Second-year students and First-year students. In addition, it has only an influence on the Fourth-year students. Also, financial capability is influential on the all-year levels. In terms of personal gain, it is considered very highly influential to Third-year students, Second-year students, Fourth-year students, and First-year students. Furthermore, fun and travel are highly influential to second and Third-year students. At the same time, it is highly influential to First-year and Fourth-year students.

There is a significant difference between the level of influence of encouragement to others to students' participation when grouped according to year level. In terms of encouragement to others, Third-year is the most influenced by the stated factor to participate in students' educational tours, followed by the Second-year, First-year, and Fourth-year. On the other hand, there is no significant difference between the level of influence of socialization, financial capability, personal gain, and fun and travel to students' participation on educational tours when grouped according to year level.

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